

Evolution of Transferable and Self-Organized Communication Modules for Solving Multiple Swarm Robotics Tasks

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Abstract—A key aspect of decentralized multirobot coordination is communication. However, beyond simple signaling, there are only few reports in the literature on the successful evolution of communication, with successes largely dependent on specific tasks and evolutionary setups. Thus, there is a lack of standardized communication frameworks that can be applied to different tasks without the need to redesign, rebuild, or re-evolve the entire system for every new task. In this article, we propose a novel communication module that does not need to be modified for its use in different tasks. Each robot has a coordinate (state) in a virtual communication space. The communication space is partitioned into virtual regions, and each region is linked to a physical behavior, such as seeking resources, phototaxis, or recharging the battery. A robot’s individual behavior is determined by the region to which its current communication state belongs. Since robots can navigate the communication space and continually broadcast their coordinates to neighbors within range, robot swarms can effectively coordinate their behavior in a self-organized manner. We demonstrate that the same evolved communication module is effective in three swarm robotics tasks: 1) the physical aggregation of the robots into groups of a desired size; 2) the formation of desired swarm geometries; and 3) a foraging task based on temporal role allocation. The results show that the communication module provides good and scalable performance in all tasks, representing a significant step toward a task-agnostic communication framework for robot swarms.

Index Terms—Collaborative intelligence, communication systems, distributed management, evolutionary robotics, formation control, swarm robotics.

I. INTRODUCTION

COMMUNICATION is one of the key pillars in swarm robotics (SR) [1], [2] that is required to effectively

Received 10 October 2024; revised 18 March 2025 and 1 September 2025; accepted 5 September 2025. This work was supported in part by the European Commission within the context of the project SMAUG, through EU Horizon Europe under Grant 101121129; in part by the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 under Grant PID2023-146540OB-C42; and in part by the Independent Research Fund Denmark under Grant 0136-00251B. The work of Rafael Sendra-Arranz was supported by the “Programa Propio I+D+i” financed by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. This article was recommended by Associate Editor P. Shi. (*Corresponding author: Rafael Sendra-Arranz.*)

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Color versions of one or more figures in this article are available at <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2025.3610013>.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/TCYB.2025.3610013

solve many cooperative tasks (e.g., [3], [4], and [5]). Interrobot communication can potentially be any sort of information exchange among the robots of the swarm. In SR, communication can be categorized as either *direct interaction* [6], [7], [8], *stigmergy* [9], [10], [11], or *direct communication* [3], [4], [5]. The third category, *direct communication*, requires explicit transmission and processing of signals whose meaning is correlated to the specific task. There are multiple works in the literature that employ direct communication in SR tasks, with diverse communication technologies and different emergent or designed communication semantics (e.g., [4], [5], [12], [13], [14], and [15]). Unfortunately, the communication mechanics and semantics in these SR works are specifically designed *ad hoc* for the task or problem studied [16]. This approach represents a significant challenge in the SR field, as there is a lack of standardized communication frameworks or methods that can be implemented across a wide variety of problems. This issue is also discussed in [17], highlighting the relation between the lack of standardization and real-world applicability in the SRs field. Therefore, designing and evolving SR communication systems and mechanics that are task agnostic is a key challenge in the field.

In this article, we propose a self-organized and decentralized communication module whose logic is evolved only once and can be used in different SR tasks and with varying swarm sizes without modification. We demonstrate this valuable feature by employing the exact same evolved communication module in three well-known SR problems, namely, aggregation of the robots into groups of desired sizes, formation control, and a foraging task involving dynamic role allocation. We show that these distinct tasks can be successfully solved using the proposed system.

The communication module is based on a virtual state space, referred to as the *communication space*. Each robot has a coordinate in this communication space that corresponds to its *communication state*. The communication space is partitioned into regions, each of which is associated with a physical behavior—for example, behaviors, such as “follow another robot” or “go to a light source.” Each robot executes the behavior associated with the region that contains its current communication state. Robots can dynamically change their communication state by virtually navigating in the communication space. Furthermore, at each control cycle, every robot

communicates its communication state to its neighbors within range. Robots can use the received states to coordinate their virtual navigation with other robots in order to solve SR tasks. For example, in a multiplace foraging task, we demonstrate how robots can use the communication module to coordinate and decide which robots forage from each food source.

The transferability of robot behaviors has been addressed by multiple authors in the literature. Kegeleirs et al. [18] define two types of transferability: 1) design-method transfer and 2) embodiment transfer. The former refers to the ability to use the same automatic design method to generate robot controllers for different platforms or tasks, while the latter implies transferring and deploying the robot controller across multiple scenarios. In this article, we focus on embodiment transfer, slightly extending the definition in [18] toward communication transferability—the reuse of the same evolved communication across multiple missions. Hasselmann et al. [19] proposed an automatic and modular design method for robot swarms that minimizes human intervention. Probabilistic finite-state machines (PFSMs) were automatically built for different tasks using ANN-based, mission-agnostic behaviors. However, the tasks considered in this work did not require explicit communication and, therefore, communication transfer was not necessary. Salman et al. [20] proposed the automatic design of stigmergic communication and its application to a wide variety of tasks. Even though they achieved automatic communication design and its application to multiple tasks, the optimization of communication must still be restarted on a per-mission basis (design-method transfer).

Previous studies have reported the use of virtual structures to coordinate robot swarms [21], [22], [23], [24], [25]. Nonetheless, these virtual constructs are used as tools for planning robot motion rather than as a means of communication. A related approach was proposed in [26] and extended in [27]. The authors introduced a self-organized division of labor framework, called *partitioning social inhibition*. Inspired by the division of labor in honeybees, each robot acquires its role according to a density-based distribution along a virtual segment. In this article, we also use a virtual space for coordination. However, there are several differences. First, we explore self-organization at the robot level rather than at the group level, which allows each robot to specialize inherently in different roles. Second, we focus on the generalization of the proposed communication module across different SR tasks. Third, Zahadat et al. [26], [27] restricted the virtual space to a segment, which is convenient for small swarms but may degrade performance as swarm size and role diversity increase. Here, we consider both 1-D and 2-D spaces, which significantly reduces the time required to switch between tasks and improves overall system convergence. Finally, in Section V, we experimentally demonstrate that our system achieves faster convergence in the self-organization process, a critical feature in SR systems.

This article introduces a self-organized communication module for robot swarms that can successfully be used in diverse SR tasks. The main contributions are the following.

- 1) *Transferability in SR*: The communication is evolved only once and transferred to multiple SR tasks.

- 2) *New Communication Paradigm*: Introduction of a novel, self-organized, and decentralized communication module for robot swarms, based on a virtual construct that robots use to communicate, interact, and solve common tasks.
- 3) Performance and transferability is demonstrated in three popular SR tasks: a) aggregation; b) formation control; and c) foraging.
- 4) *Scalability*: The results show good performance and scalability in swarms of up to 60 robots, which lays the groundwork for solving many other SR tasks.

II. COMMUNICATION MODULE

Inspired by the fields of cooperative control [28] and graph neural networks [29], we propose a transferable decentralized communication module for solving SR tasks. It is based on a virtual communication state space, or simply *communication space*, where each robot has its own *communication state*. The communication space is a purely abstract construct with no direct physical counterpart—it does not represent a spatial mapping, topology, or replica of the real world in any way. The communication states are the only pieces of information communicated between the robots. Robots can change their communication state via *virtual navigation*. We categorize the *communication module* as the combination of the communication space, the robots' *virtual navigation* in that space, and the communication of states between neighboring robots.

A. Communication State Space

Let \mathcal{S} be the communication space. We consider the partition \mathcal{R} of \mathcal{S} introduced as follows:

$$\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_M\} | \mathcal{S} = \mathcal{R}_1 \cup \mathcal{R}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{R}_M. \quad (1)$$

Moreover, each region \mathcal{R}_j , with $j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, is represented by a centroid or virtual landmark $l_j \in \mathcal{R}_j$. Using these virtual landmarks, a convenient way to define the regions is shown as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}_j = \{\mathbf{s} \in \mathcal{S} \mid d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}, l_j) < d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}, l_k) \forall k \neq j\} \quad (2)$$

where $d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}')$ refers to some distance metric within \mathcal{S} . In the special case in which $d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}, l_j) = d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}, l_k)$, the region is assigned randomly to one of the candidate regions.

We define $\mathbf{s}_i \in \mathcal{S}$ as the communication state of the i th robot, considering $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, where N is the number of robots or swarm size. Additionally, each robot has a virtual orientation ($\theta_i(t)$), which defines its direction of movement within the virtual space \mathcal{S} . A robot i is in region \mathcal{R}_j at time instant t provided that $\mathbf{s}_i(t) \in \mathcal{R}_j$.

$f_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathbf{s}_i) = \mathcal{R}_k \iff \mathbf{s}_i \in \mathcal{R}_k$, where the function $f_{\mathcal{R}}$ determines the virtual region to which a given robot's state belongs. Each virtual region corresponds to a physical behavior. Moreover, robots communicate their individual state (coordinate in the communication space) to neighbors in range.

Fig. 1(a) illustrates a 1-D communication space with six virtual regions $\{\mathcal{R}_i\}_{i=1}^6$ represented by their associated virtual landmarks $\{l_i\}_{i=1}^6$. In this example, there are eight robots whose communication states are represented by white circles. In this

Fig. 1. Hypothetical communication spaces and primitive selector. (a) Hypothetical 1-D communication space with six virtual regions (\mathcal{R}_i) and their respective landmarks l_i (denoted as stars). (b) Hypothetical 2-D communication space with six virtual regions as in (a). In both (a) and (b), there are eight robots, whose communication states are represented as white circles. (c) Example of a primitive selector that maps virtual regions in \mathcal{S} to primitives f_i to be executed by the robots. (d) Screenshot of the eight robots executing their corresponding primitives. The geometric shape displayed on top of each robot represents the primitive being executed, while the color of the robot's LED indicates its current virtual region (according to the colors shown in (a) and (b)).

figure, there is one robot in \mathcal{R}_1 , two in \mathcal{R}_2 , two are in \mathcal{R}_3 , two in \mathcal{R}_4 , one in \mathcal{R}_6 , and none in \mathcal{R}_5 . Additionally, Fig. 1(b) illustrates the analogous 2-D communication space with the same number of virtual regions and landmarks.

B. Connection Between Virtual Regions and Robot Behaviors

Similar to the levels of competence in [30] and the behavior primitives in [31], we define a *primitive pool* $\mathcal{F} = \{f_1, \dots, f_K\}$, which is a set of primitive behaviors designed to solve specific and simple tasks. Some examples of primitives are “explore the arena,” “approach a light source” (*phototaxis*), “move away from a light source,” “follow another robot,” “stay in a nest,” and “forage from a resource area.” These primitives have access to the robot sensor readings and can modify the state of the robot's actuators. In this article, we only consider manually designed primitives, but the set could also include evolved, learned, or hybrid primitives. Each virtual region is associated with exactly one behavior primitive. We therefore define a mapping between the virtual regions in \mathcal{R} and the primitives in \mathcal{F} . This implies that a robot whose communication state belongs to a virtual region executes the primitive for that region. We refer to this mapping between the sets \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{F} as the *primitive selector*. In this article, every robot has the same set of primitives, and the primitives and primitive selector are manually designed for each specific task being solved. An example of a primitive selector is illustrated in Fig. 1(c), where six virtual regions of either Fig. 1(a) or (b) are mapped onto four primitives $\{f_1, \dots, f_4\}$ (represented graphically as different geometric shapes). Fig. 1(d) shows a swarm of eight robots that are solving a certain task. The primitive that each robot of the figure is executing is graphically represented with a 3-D geometry according to the robot's communication state in Figs. 1(a) and (b) and the primitive selector in Fig. 1(c).

C. Navigation in the Communication Space

The communication state of each robot is subject to *virtual navigation* that modifies its coordinates in \mathcal{S} . Furthermore, a

navigation policy defines the rules and dynamics of virtual navigation, which are driven by a goal or convergence criterion. To be effective, such navigation policy should take into consideration the virtual landmarks and the communication states of the neighbors (with neighborhood in the communication space defined as follows)

$$s_i, s_j \text{ are neighbors} \iff f_{\mathcal{R}}(s_i) = f_{\mathcal{R}}(s_j). \quad (3)$$

In this article, we establish the navigation policy goal as follows:

$$\forall s_i, s_j \in \{s_1, \dots, s_N\}, s_i \neq s_j \Rightarrow f_{\mathcal{R}}(s_i) \neq f_{\mathcal{R}}(s_j). \quad (4)$$

This target condition is met when each robot's communication state belongs to a unique virtual region, ensuring no two robots share the same region. To complement (4), notice that the virtual regions form a partition of \mathcal{S} , so that any communication state always belongs to only one virtual region, regardless of the navigation policy. The navigation goal in (4) has been deliberately established to solve the SR tasks of this article. However, alternative objectives can be designed to meet other task requirements (e.g., allowing multiple robots' communication states to converge to the same virtual region).

To fulfill the imposed policy, the virtual navigation is controlled by the *communication controller* (f_{comm}). The communication controller is a distinct unit and should not be confused with the conventional controller responsible for the robot's physical behavior. The latter maps sensor readings to actuator actions, while the former governs the virtual navigation of the robots in the communication space. The communication controller of the i th robot is generically defined as follows:

$$a_i, \theta_{\text{tar},i} = f_{\text{comm}}(s_i, s_{\text{cst}}, l_{\text{cst}}, l_{\text{tar}}) \quad (5)$$

where the outputs are the normalized navigation speed $a_i \in [0, 1]$ and the target virtual orientation $\theta_{\text{tar},i}$ of robot i in the communication space \mathcal{S} . Alternatively, the communication controller receives as inputs four vectors, namely, the closest

communication state among the neighbors in \mathcal{S} (\mathbf{s}_{cst}), the closest landmark (l_{cst} , which is the landmark associated with the virtual region $f_{\mathcal{R}}(s_i)$), a target landmark (l_{tar}), and its own communication state (s_i). The tuple $(s_i, \mathbf{s}_{\text{cst}}, l_{\text{cst}}, l_{\text{tar}})$ summarizes all the information required by f_{comm} to fulfill (4), while avoiding the high dimensionality and dynamic size issues that would arise if all the virtual landmarks and all the neighbor communication states were provided.

Before explaining the computation of the target landmark l_{tar} , let $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{N}_0^M$ ($\mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup 0$) be a vector of priorities, where 0 represents the highest priority, and priority decreases with increasing numbers. The priorities in \mathbf{p}_i are associated one-to-one with each of the virtual regions, so that $\mathbf{p}_i(m)$ is the priority of region \mathcal{R}_m for all $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ according to robot i . The subscript i of \mathbf{p}_i is used to denote that the priorities are subjective to each robot $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, so that each robot can have different virtual region priorities (see Sections II-D and II-E for more details).

The target landmark (l_{tar}) is selected according to the following criteria, listed according to their importance in the selection.

- 1) Whether the virtual region \mathcal{R}_{tar} of l_{tar} is already occupied by one or more neighbors.
- 2) The priority of the landmark's region.
- 3) The distance, $d_{\mathcal{S}}$, from the robot's communication state to the landmark.

The communication controller is responsible for generating a virtual navigation velocity and orientation. The dynamics of the virtual orientation of a robot i are characterized as follows:

$$\tau_{\theta} \frac{\partial \theta_i(t)}{\partial t} = \theta_{\text{tar},i}(t) - \theta_i(t) \quad (6)$$

while the dynamics of the communication state are defined as follows:

$$\tau_s \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_i(t)}{\partial t} = a_i(t) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_i(t)) \\ \sin(\theta_i(t)) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

The fixed time constants τ_{θ} and τ_s also influence the linear and angular speeds of the virtual navigation, and are set to $20 \cdot \partial t$ in both cases. Preliminary studies revealed that they are a good tradeoff between smoothness and fast response in the virtual navigation.

Equations (6) and (7) are specifically designed for 2-D communication spaces. Thus, in the case of 1-D communication spaces, the dynamics reduce to (8) as there is no longer a need to include orientation

$$\tau_s \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_i(t)}{\partial t} = a_i(t) \cdot \theta_{\text{tar},i}(t). \quad (8)$$

In (8), the variable $\theta_{\text{tar},i} \in \{-1, 1\}$ has two possible values, each representing one of the two navigation directions along the single dimension of the communication space.

Fig. 2(a) summarizes the stages of the virtual navigation process of a robot in the communication space. First, \mathbf{s}_{cst} , l_{cst} , and l_{tar} are computed. Subsequently, these vectors are fed to the communication controller f_{comm} , which generates the desired navigation speed and virtual orientation. The communication state of the robot is ultimately updated based on (6) and (7).

Fig. 2. Diagram of the overall system. (a) Communication module. (b) Robot controller.

D. Robot Controller

The robot controller, illustrated in Fig. 2(b), is responsible for the physical behavior of a robot. In each control cycle, the primitive selector is used to pick one of the primitives available in a *primitive pool*, based on the current region of the robot in the communication space. Moreover, the selected primitive is executed using the current sensory readings, denoted as $\phi(t)$. In addition, the robot controller is also composed by the *priority selector*. A virtual region's priority determines its relative importance for a given robot and is considered when the robot performs virtual navigation. The priority selector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_i(t) = \text{PrioritySelector}(\phi(t)) \quad (9)$$

so that its outcome is the vector \mathbf{p}_i , resulting from the concatenation of the priorities of all the primitives of the i th robot. The priorities can be set to fixed values, for instance, as in the aggregation and formation tasks (see Sections IV-A and IV-B). However, priorities can also be dynamically updated using conditional rules and the current sensor readings, $\phi(t)$. As an example, a change in the priority of a primitive can happen when a robot runs low on battery and needs to critically prioritize a “recharge battery” behavior. In this scenario, the priority selector would simply check whether some battery level threshold was crossed, and modify the “recharge battery” priority accordingly.

E. Interactions Between the Communication Module and the Robot Controller

Fig. 2 shows an overview of the communication module, the robot controller, and the data flow between them. The bidirectional interactions between these two components are the following.

- 1) *Influence of the Communication Module on the Robot Controller*: The communication module modifies the behavior of the robots in the physical environment through the primitive selector and the communication state. Specifically, the communication state of a

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the communication module phases.

robot and the virtual region to which it belongs determine the physical behavior primitive executed by a robot. Similarly, transitioning from one virtual region to another also causes a change in the robot's physical behavior.

- 2) *Influence of the Robot Controller on the Communication Module*: The robot controller can alter the virtual navigation that characterizes the communication module by means of the priority vector $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$ local to each robot i . Consequently, $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$ of a robot i determines the virtual regions that this robot should occupy with highest priority at time instant t . The robot controller can modify the values of \mathbf{p}_i at each control cycle based on the sensor readings.

F. Evolution and Deployment Phases

The parameters of the ANN defining the communication controller (f_{comm}) are optimized with the ultimate goal of satisfying (4). The communication controller is evolved prior to the design of the physical robot controller. Accordingly, it operates in two stages: 1) the *evolution phase* and 2) the *deployment phase*.

The *evolution phase* focuses exclusively on optimizing the communication controller, where robots learn to navigate in the communication space. At this stage, the controller is agnostic to the SR task performed in the physical environment, and no primitive behaviors are associated with the virtual regions.

The *deployment phase* begins once evolution is complete. Here, the communication module is configured for a specific SR task by assigning primitive behaviors to virtual regions and defining both the primitive selector and the priority selector. While this study employs manually designed primitives and selectors, these components could also be evolved or learned depending on task-specific requirements.

A key advantage of the proposed module is its task-agnostic nature: it can be reused across diverse tasks without redesign, re-evolution, or retraining, a property we refer to as *transferability* [18]. Adapting the module to a new task requires only its configuration during deployment. In this study, we evolve a single communication controller and deploy it across multiple tasks: aggregation, formation control, and foraging (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. Example showing how the communication module and robot controller can solve a simple foraging. (a) Communication space showing example trajectories of two cooperating robots solving a simple foraging. (b) Primitive selector showing five primitive behaviors (f_i) and how they are associated to the regions of the communication space. It also provides a short description of each goal of each primitive. (a) also shows multiple callouts with the values of the priorities of the robots during specific parts of the trajectories (illustrated with the style of the curves, being either solid, dashed, or dotted). For the sake of clarity, in this example we consider either ON and OFF priority values, so that ON means that the corresponding region has priority and the robot is attracted to it, and OFF implies that the corresponding region can be neglected. For example, the vector (OFF, OFF, OFF, OFF, ON) indicates that only region \mathcal{R}_5 has priority, and thus, the robot's target behavior would be f_5 ("Return to nest").

G. Illustrative Example

A simple multiplace foraging task is used as an example to illustrate the operation of the communication module. This foraging task is composed of a nest zone and two food areas. The aim of the robots is to find the food areas and, thereafter, transport as many food elements as possible to the nest by performing round trips between the corresponding resource area and the nest. Additionally, the robots must perform continual task allocation so that each robot seeks and forages from a different food area.

This example with two robots is shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4(a) depicts the communication space and the virtual navigation of each of the two robots (as white and black curves, respectively). There are five virtual regions ($\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_5$), each linked to a distinct primitive behavior (f_1, \dots, f_5) according to the primitive selector shown in Fig. 4(b). The callouts show the 5-D priority vectors with their values set to either OFF or ON for each of the five regions. The style of the curve (dotted, dashed, or solid) depicts the part of the trajectories in which the priorities of the callouts are used by each robot. The value OFF means that the robot's virtual navigation will not be attracted toward it. For example, the vector (OFF, OFF, OFF, OFF, ON) indicates that only region \mathcal{R}_5 has priority, while the rest can be neglected. Consequently, the

robot should navigate toward \mathcal{R}_5 with the aim of executing behavior f_5 (“Return to nest”).

Focusing on the trajectory of robot 1 (in white), the virtual navigation is the sequence $\{\mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_3, \mathcal{R}_5, \mathcal{R}_3, \mathcal{R}_5, \dots\}$, so that the primitives executed by this robot are $\{f_1, f_3, f_5, f_3, f_5, \dots\}$. In terms of robot behaviors, this sequence is as follows: 1) the robot searches for a food area by exploring the environment, and once food area 1 is found, 2) it continually transports resources from that food area to the nest. The virtual navigation of robot 2 (in black) is the series $\{\mathcal{R}_2, \mathcal{R}_4, \mathcal{R}_5, \mathcal{R}_4, \mathcal{R}_5, \dots\}$ and the sequence of robot 2 primitives are $\{f_2, f_4, f_5, f_4, f_5, \dots\}$. In this case, robot 2 starts executing the primitive “Find food area 2,” because robot 1 is already looking for the other food source. Subsequently, robot 2 performs a round trip foraging from the food area 2 and the nest. The values of the priority vectors play a crucial role in this example. For instance, the round trips between \mathcal{R}_3 and \mathcal{R}_5 are produced because when a robot acquires food, the robot controller updates the priority vector to (OFF, OFF, OFF, OFF, ON), indicating that only region \mathcal{R}_5 is active, and the new target behavior of the robot is returning to the nest (primitive f_5).

III. EVOLUTION OF THE COMMUNICATION CONTROLLER

The communication module, f_{comm} , should enable robots to virtually navigate the communication space in a manner that satisfies (4). For f_{comm} , we use an ANN whose parameters and topology are evolved using the neuroevolution of augmenting topologies (NEAT) algorithm [32]. Even though f_{comm} can, in principle, be optimized using other evolutionary algorithms that target fixed neural structures, the use of NEAT is motivated by its ability to simultaneously evolve both ANN parameters and topology. NEAT begins with minimal architectures and progressively increases the number of neurons and synapses, seeking balance between performance and complexity. Moreover, NEAT incorporates niching strategies that promote model diversity and alleviate premature convergence to suboptimal solutions.

In each generation of NEAT, every individual is evaluated in a robotics simulator (see Section IV). In each simulation, a swarm of ten robots navigates a virtual communication space divided into ten regions. At each control cycle, every robot transmits its communication state (s_i) to neighboring robots. One iteration of the communication module [with its control flow and main stages shown in Fig. 2(a)] is then computed, producing the next communication state for each robot.

The objective of evolution in this study is to optimize the communication controller so that robots are distributed with exactly one robot per region, thereby satisfying (4). The initial communication states of the robots are uniformly distributed across the entire communication space. The coordinates of the virtual landmarks in the communication space are also randomly sampled, subject to a minimum distance constraint between landmarks. This minimum distance is a hyperparameter that depends on the total number of landmarks. For ten landmarks, we empirically set this value to 0.3, ensuring sufficient separation between landmarks.

Fig. 5. Communication space configuration, topologies, and virtual navigation control. (a) Circle communication space embedded in a 3-D space. Remark: the thickness of the circle is only represented for visualization purposes, albeit the structure is a compact 1-D manifold. (b) Unfolded circle communication space. (c) Torus communication space embedded in a 3-D space. (d) Unfolded torus communication space. (e) Architecture of the CTRNN model used to control the virtual navigation of the robots in the communication space.

A. Communication Space

The communication framework is assessed in experiments with both 1-D and 2-D communication spaces. We define the 1-D communication space as the line segment $\mathcal{S}_1 = [-L/2, L/2]$ with the additional property that the two endpoints $-L/2$ and $L/2$ are connected—in fact, they are the same point in the communication space. Fig. 5(a) shows the 1-D communication space as a circle in a 2-D space, while Fig. 5(b) illustrates it as a line segment. Both representations correspond to the same communication space. The distance metric that characterizes \mathcal{S}_1 is defined as follows:

$$d_{\mathcal{S}_1}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') = \min\{|\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'|, L - |\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'|\} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{S}_1$.

The 2-D communication space is defined as an unfolded torus in $\mathcal{S}_2 = [-W/2, W/2] \times [-H/2, H/2]$. The upper and lower boundaries of \mathcal{S}_2 are connected, and the left and right boundaries are connected as well. Fig. 5(c) shows \mathcal{S}_2 as a torus in a 3-D space, while Fig. 5(d) illustrates the unfolded torus. As in the 1-D case, the communication spaces represented in both figures are equivalent. The distance metric of \mathcal{S}_2 is formulated as follows:

$$d_{\mathcal{S}_2}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') = \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \min\{|\mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}'_1|, W - |\mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}'_1|\} \\ \min\{|\mathbf{s}_2 - \mathbf{s}'_2|, H - |\mathbf{s}_2 - \mathbf{s}'_2|\} \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2 \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{s} = (\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2)^\top$ and $\mathbf{s}' = (\mathbf{s}'_1, \mathbf{s}'_2)^\top$ and $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}' \in \mathcal{S}_2$.

B. Communication Controller

The ANN model used in f_{comm} is the continuous-time recurrent neural network (CTRNN) [33], which is an ANN with feedback connections that operates in continuous time. The use of a CTRNN is motivated by the continuous dynamics of virtual navigation in the communication space, which presents a scenario where a reactive feed-forward model may not suffice.

Fig. 5(e) shows the CTRNN architecture used in the experiments. The bottom nodes of the figure represent the input neurons of the neural network, and the top nodes represent the output neurons. Recall from Section II-C that f_{comm} receives

as input the closest neighbor's communication state (\mathbf{s}_{cst}), the closest landmark (l_{cst}), and the target landmark (l_{tar}). The CTRNN execution is preceded by a preprocessing stage in which these vectors are converted into the distance and angle between the robot communication state and the corresponding vector. For instance, $d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_{\text{cst}})$ and $\varphi_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_{\text{cst}})$ are, respectively, the distance and angle between \mathbf{s}_i and \mathbf{s}_{cst} in \mathcal{S} . In contrast, the outputs of the CTRNN are the virtual navigation velocity and target orientation for robot i .

C. Evolutionary Setup

The fitness function FF_i enforces that only one robot should occupy each virtual region in order to achieve the goal defined in (4). The instantaneous fitness function of a single robot i , used by the NEAT algorithm to optimize the CTRNN model, is shown as follows:

$$FF_i(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-\alpha \cdot d_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{s}_i(t), l_i^*(t))}, & \text{if } \mathbf{s}_j \notin \mathcal{R}_i^*(t) \ \forall j \neq i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_i^*(t)$ is the virtual region to which the communication state of robot i currently belongs ($\mathbf{s}_i \in \mathcal{R}_i^*$ at time step t), and l_i^* refers to the virtual landmark corresponding to region \mathcal{R}_i^* .

The value of FF_i increases exponentially as the distance to l_i^* decreases, provided that robot i is the only robot whose communication state lies within virtual region \mathcal{R}_i^* . The parameter α modulates the rate at which fitness decays as the distance to the virtual landmark increases. Based on preliminary experiments, we set $\alpha = 8$ to avoid sparse fitness landscapes while preventing robots from being overly rewarded when located at the borders of the virtual regions. The final fitness score of a simulation is computed as the average of $FF_i(t)$ across all robots in the swarm and all simulation time steps. Additionally, the fitness function is evaluated ten times (*runs*), with random and independent initializations.

The NEAT population is composed of 100 individuals, with two elites preserved across generations. Maintaining two elites was found to improve performance in preliminary experiments. Each parameter of the CTRNN model is mutated with probability 0.1, using Gaussian mutation with a mutation power of 0.05. Furthermore, a new node is added with probability 0.05, and a new synaptic connection is created with probability 0.2. The remaining hyperparameters follow the configuration proposed by the authors of NEAT [32] and by previous studies of NEAT applied to SR [34]. Specifically, we use $c_1 = 1$, $c_2 = 1$, and $c_3 = 0.4$ as the compatibility coefficients, and $\delta_t = 3$ as the compatibility threshold. These parameters are used during the speciation process to identify compatible species. The weights and biases are constrained to the range $[-10, 10]$ and initialized with a Gaussian distribution of zero mean and standard deviation $\sigma = 1$.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

To assess the communication framework, we use three popular SR tasks: 1) aggregation; 2) geometric formations; and 3) foraging with robot battery dependence. We use the

same communication module, evolved according to the details and hyperparameters presented in Section III, for all tasks, but configured with different behavior primitives, primitive selector, and priority selector for each task. All the experiments are implemented using the `pybullet` library [35] for real-time collision detection and multiphysics simulations. The robots are equipped with eight IR-based proximity sensors distributed along their perimeter, a GPS to know their absolute position in the arena, and communication transmitters and receivers that enable the sharing of their communication states with neighbors within range. In the case of the foraging experiment, each robot is also equipped with eight light sensors positioned along its perimeter and a ground sensor that detects the color of the floor below the robot. Communication ranges of 2 m are used in experiments with swarm sizes below 20, while the communication range is increased to 4 m when swarm sizes larger than 20 are considered. The robotics simulations, NEAT algorithm, CTRNN models, and robot and communication controllers are public and available in a github repository called `Mereli`.¹

A. Aggregation in Groups

In the aggregation task, robots have to form a desired number of groups with a given number of robots in each group. Moreover, the robots of each group have to aggregate as closely as possible to the other members of their group, while avoiding collisions. We define G as the number of groups, and $G_i, i \in \{1, \dots, G\}$ as the number of target members of each group. Thereafter, there are G primitives with the following meanings:

$$f_i \longrightarrow \text{“Go to the center of mass coordinates of the neighbors also belonging to group } i\text{.”}$$

The number of virtual regions of the communication space equals the swarm size and, for each i , the primitive selector maps G_i different virtual regions to the primitive f_i . Fig. 6(a) illustrates an example of the aggregation in groups with 21 robots, $G = 3$ groups, three primitives $\{f_1, f_2, f_3\}$, and $G_i = 7 \ \forall i$. All the target groups of this task have the same importance and all the virtual region priorities are fixed to the same value of 1. Therefore, the priority selector used in this experiment is simply

$$\mathbf{p}_i(t) = (1, \dots, 1) \ \forall t \ \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (13)$$

At the beginning of the task execution, the target number of groups and robots per group is manually set. The robots' positions are initialized randomly within a square area of either 2×2 m for swarms with less than 20 robots, or 3×3 m for swarm sizes greater than 20. The orientations of the robots are randomly initialized between 0 and 2π . The aggregation in groups is a highly important task that goes beyond simple aggregation, as it can be used to conveniently divide the labor of the swarm across teams in real-world geographically distributed tasks [36], [37], such as firefighting or search and rescue.

¹<https://github.com/Robolabo/Mereli/tree/VCommModule>

Fig. 6. Illustration of the proposed SR experiments. (a) Aggregation in groups of desired sizes. (b) Formation of target swarm geometries. (c) Basic foraging with a nest area (black), two food areas (gray), and three red light sources where the robots can recharge their batteries. The aim is to perform a temporal role allocation so that there are always $N/4$ robots foraging from each of the resources ($N/2$ foragers in total), while the remaining swarm members are either recharging their batteries or waiting inside the nest.

B. Formation

The second task is the formation of desired swarm geometries (e.g., [38] and [39]). The formation is relative to the center of mass of the robots, implying that it can be established anywhere in the environment. The only requirement is that the distances between robots are approximately preserved according to the geometry of the specified formation. As an example, Fig. 6(b) illustrates a target formation with nine robots.

Let the target formation of N points be formulated as follows:

$$\{\mathbf{x}_1^*(t), \dots, \mathbf{x}_N^*(t)\} = \{\mathbf{c}(t) + \Delta_1, \dots, \mathbf{c}(t) + \Delta_N\} \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the center of mass of the swarm and $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, $\Delta_i \in \mathbb{R}_+^2$ is the offset vector that defines the coordinates of the point \mathbf{x}_i^* relative to \mathbf{c} in the formation.

In this experiment, the primitive selector is an injective mapping between $\mathcal{R} = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_N\}$ and $\mathcal{F} = \{f_1, \dots, f_N\}$, so that each primitive has the following meaning:

$$f_i \longrightarrow \text{“Go to coordinates } \mathbf{x}_i^*(t) = \mathbf{c}(t) + \Delta_i \text{”}.$$

All the spots of the target formation have the same importance and, therefore, all the virtual region priorities are fixed to the same value of 1 [see (13)]. At the beginning of the task execution, the target formation geometry is manually set. Moreover, robots’ physical positions and orientations are randomly initialized as in the aggregation task (Section IV-A).

C. Foraging

The third task is foraging. The environment has a nest area and two resource areas located at opposites sides of the nest. Additionally, each robot is equipped with a battery that discharges when the robot is outside the nest and can be recharged in the proximity of a light source. The aim is to maintain 25% of the robots foraging from food 1 and another 25% that forage from food 2. The remaining 50% of the robots either wait inside the nest or recharge their batteries. Thus, there are four roles engaged by the robots, namely: *stay in nest*, *forage food 1*, *forage food 2*, and *recharge battery*. Note that this task requires dynamic role allocation because when a forager robot runs low on battery and goes to recharge,

another idling robot has to update its role to forage in its place. Fig. 6(c) depicts the foraging experiment with $N = 12$ robots accomplishing the task with the optimal distribution of roles. The figure also illustrates the locations of the nest (black ground area), the food areas (gray ground areas), and the red light sources where the robots can recharge their batteries.

The battery level of each robot i is denoted as $b_i(t) \in [0, 1]$ and is subject to the dynamics in (15) and (16) for its charge and discharge, respectively

$$\frac{\partial b(t)}{\partial t} = \gamma (1 - b(t)^2) \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial b(t)}{\partial t} = \Delta b \quad (16)$$

where γ and Δb are the charge and discharge coefficients, and as initial conditions, we fix $b(0) = 1$.

There are $N + 1$ virtual regions, and we define four behavior primitives

- $f_1 \longrightarrow \text{“Stay in the nest area,”}$
- $f_2 \longrightarrow \text{“Forage from food area 1,”}$
- $f_3 \longrightarrow \text{“Forage from food area 2,”}$
- $f_4 \longrightarrow \text{“Recharge battery (phototaxis).”}$

Additionally, the primitive selector performs the following mapping between virtual regions and primitives:

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{nest}} = \{\mathcal{R}_1, \dots, \mathcal{R}_{\frac{N}{2}}\} \longrightarrow f_1$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{food1}} = \{\mathcal{R}_{\frac{N}{2}+1}, \dots, \mathcal{R}_{\frac{3N}{4}}\} \longrightarrow f_2$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{food2}} = \{\mathcal{R}_{\frac{3N}{4}+1}, \dots, \mathcal{R}_N\} \longrightarrow f_3$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{bat}} = \mathcal{R}_{N+1} \longrightarrow f_4.$$

By default, the priorities of each virtual region are 2 for the regions in $\mathcal{R}_{\text{nest}}$, 1 in the case of $\mathcal{R}_{\text{food1}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{food2}}$, and 3 for \mathcal{R}_{bat} . Consequently, foraging from one of the food areas has the highest priority, staying in the nest has medium priority, and recharging the battery is a low-priority primitive. Nonetheless, when the condition $b_i(t) < 0.4$ is met, the priority of \mathcal{R}_{bat} is updated to 0, turning battery recovery into the primitive with highest priority. When the battery level is above

Fig. 7. Results of communication module in isolation. (a) Results of three independent simulations of the virtual navigation in the 1-D communication space \mathcal{S}_1 with ten virtual landmarks and ten robots. (b) Results of the virtual navigation in the 2-D communication space \mathcal{S}_2 with 20 virtual regions and 20 robots. Red stars indicate the coordinates of the virtual landmarks and circles represent the communication states of the robots. (c) Box plot showing the evolution of the number of errors in the virtual navigation during a simulation with 30 robots. An error occurs when a robot moves into a virtual region that is occupied by another robot.

0.9 again, the priorities for the corresponding robot return to their default values. Specifically, the following priority selector is used in the foraging task:

$$\mathbf{p}_i(t) = \begin{cases} \left(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{N/2}, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{N/2}, 3 \right), & \text{if battery recharged} \\ \left(\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{N/2}, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{N/2}, 0 \right), & \text{if battery depleted.} \end{cases}$$

The environment is composed of a nest area (circular black ground area), two food areas (circular gray ground areas) of equal radius, and three red light sources that can be sensed from every point in the environment (see Fig. 6). The nest area is always located at the center of the arena and has a radius twice as large as the food areas. Specifically, the nest radius is fixed to 1 m for swarm sizes smaller than 40 and 2 m for swarms with more than 40 robots. The food areas are located symmetrically at either sides of the nest, being the *nest-to-food* distance: 3 m for swarms up to 40 robots, and 5 m for swarm sizes greater than 40. The robot positions are initialized randomly within a square centered at the nest's origin, of either 2×2 and 3×3 for swarm sizes in the ranges $[1, 40)$ and $[40, 60]$, respectively. The battery is always fully charged at the beginning of every simulation, and γ and Δb are always fixed to 0.01 and 0.001.

V. RESULTS

A. Communication Module in Isolation

We first present the results of the evolved communication module in isolation, assessing whether the navigation goal in (4) is fulfilled during virtual navigation in both \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 . Focusing first on the 1-D communication space \mathcal{S}_1 , Fig. 7(a) shows the results of virtual navigation with ten virtual landmarks (red stars) and robots (white circles) across three independent executions (horizontal lines). In this case, the

Fig. 8. Results of the aggregation in groups with swarms of 20 robots. (a) Aggregation in two groups of ten robots. (b) Aggregation in three groups with irregular sizes of 5, 6, and 9 robots. (c) Aggregation in four groups of five robots. (d) Aggregation in five groups of four robots.

virtual navigation successfully meets the convergence criterion defined in (4). In addition, Fig. 7(b) depicts the results in \mathcal{S}_2 using 20 virtual regions and 20 robots. Fig. 7(c) shows the evolution of the number of errors over simulation time steps, in a swarm of 30 robots using \mathcal{S}_2 as the communication space. Every 100 time steps, the distribution of errors is summarized as a box plot based on 50 independent runs. The convergence time to reach a median error (red segments) of 5 is approximately 700 time steps, while achieving a median error of 0 requires around 2400 iterations. Moreover, the steady-state solution exhibits a stable median value of 0 and low variation.

B. Aggregation in Groups

Fig. 8 shows the positions of the robots in the final frame of simulations with 20 robots and with different numbers of groups in the aggregation task. In all the runs, the task is successfully solved, demonstrating that the swarm is capable of allocating and distributing its members to different groups to fit the target sizes. Additionally, it should be noted that the clusters of aggregated robots tend to remain dispersed, preventing cluster mergers.

C. Formation

The swarm formation task is also solved with promising results. Fig. 9(a)–(e) illustrate the convergence toward four different formation geometries, showing the trajectories as well as the initial and final formations. In all representations, the colors of the circles indicate the time instant of the corresponding formation, according to the timeline in the color bar in Fig. 9(g). The short black lines denote the orientation of the robots. All formations are reached with high accuracy, starting from randomly selected initial positions. Moreover, Fig. 9(f) presents a simulation in which the target formation is switched three times during the experiment. The desired formation geometry is set by explicitly updating the Δ_i vectors of the primitives (see Section IV-B). In real-world applications, the target geometry update could be teleoperated or preprogrammed.

In addition to formation switching, Fig. 9(f) also shows coordinated movement of the swarm while preserving the converged formation. Recall from Section IV-B that the aim of the primitives is to drive the robots toward the formation points $\{\mathbf{c}(t) + \Delta_1, \dots, \mathbf{c}(t) + \Delta_N\}$. Thus, once the swarm has successfully converged to the desired formation, the entire swarm can be controlled by simply adding an offset or bias

Fig. 9. Results of the swarm formation task. (a)–(e) Results for five different formation geometries, showing the trajectories of the robots (left), a zoomed-in view on the initial positions of the robots (upper right), and a zoomed-in view on the final formation results (bottom right). (f) Swarm switches among three different formations in the same simulation. It also shows a coordinated navigation preserving the desired formation. (g) Color bar of the simulation time line. In all the figures, the colors of the circles denote the time when the robot was in that position, according to the color bar.

to the estimated center of mass. In the coordinated navigation shown in Fig. 9(f), we modify the primitives as follows:

$$f_i \longrightarrow \text{“Go to coordinates } \mathbf{x}_i(t) = \mathbf{c}(t) + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \Delta_i\text{”}.$$

D. Foraging

The results of the foraging experiment with swarms of 40 robots are summarized in Fig. 10. Fig. 10(a) shows the distribution of roles using a ternary plot. The three axes represent the proportions of robots foraging from food 1, food 2, and those either recharging their batteries or staying in the nest. The point size indicates the number of samples with the corresponding proportions. Although some dispersion is observed, the larger points cluster around the optimal solution

$$(\text{Food 1, Food 2, Nest+Battery}) = (0.25, 0.25, 0.5).$$

On the right, Fig. 10(a) also provides a zoomed-in view of the points within the highlighted rectangle of the ternary plot, depicting the proportion of robots waiting in the nest versus recharging their batteries. In the most common scenario, 50% of the swarm waits in the nest, while no robots are low on battery. As more robots recharge, the number of individuals in the nest decreases to maintain a constant 50% of foragers.

Fig. 10(b) shows a 3-D representation of the foraging experiment. The horizontal plane at the bottom represents the flat arena where the robots move, while the colored surfaces illustrate the density of robot visits to each (x, y) coordinate of the plane throughout the simulation. There are four density surfaces—blue, green, orange, and red—corresponding to the primitives f_1 , f_2 , f_3 , and f_4 , respectively, (see Section IV-C). These density surfaces align closely with the expected robot behavior (see also Fig. 6(c) for the locations of the different arena regions).

The results in Fig. 10(a) show that the robots successfully self-organize and allocate roles during the experiment using the communication module. Fig. 10(d) illustrates time series of the proportion of robots executing each role. Two alternating types of time windows can be observed: 1) those in which all robots have fully recharged batteries (green) and 2) those in which at least one robot is running low on battery (red). In the green windows, the green and orange curves—representing the proportions of robots foraging from each food source—converge to the optimal value of 0.25. When the number of robots with depleted batteries increases (red windows), the proportions of foragers fluctuate more noticeably. Nonetheless, the robots in the nest (blue curve) compensate for the loss of active foragers, helping to maintain the green and orange curves at the target value of 0.25.

Finally, Fig. 10(c) depicts the role transitions during the simulations. It shows the percentage of robots transitioning from the nest (blue) or from recharging their batteries (red) to foraging at each food source. We distinguish between transitions to a foraging role that is already saturated (“Food 1 or 2 full”) and those to a role still requiring additional foragers (“Food 1 or 2 not full”). The widths of the arrows in the diagram indicate the frequency of transitions. Transitions from “stay in nest” to “Food 1 or 2 full” are minimal, and transitions from “recharge battery” to “Food 1 or 2 full” never occurred in the simulations. Both findings are positive, as the objective is to prevent robots from switching to foraging roles that are already filled.

E. Scalability

We assessed the scalability of the robot swarm in the three experiments. For the aggregation task, we use the error metrics

Fig. 10. Results of the foraging experiment with 40 robots. (a) Ternary plot showing the frequency of the robot distributions across the different foraging roles. The three axes, left, right, and bottom, correspond to the proportions of robots foraging from food area 1 (right), food area 2 (left), and the proportion of the robots either recharging their batteries or staying in the nest. The size of the circles indicates the number of times that the given proportion of robots engaging in each role is repeated across simulations. For instance, the most repeated division of labor (highlighted in the figure with dashed lines) corresponds to the optimal solution of 25% of robots foraging from food 1 and another 25% from food 2. (b) Surface illustrating the arena zones (XY plane) visited more frequently by the robots depending on their role (see legend). (c) Circular plot showing the transitions among the roles engaged by the robots in the foraging task. Specifically, it shows the transitions between the roles *Nest* and *Recharge battery* and foraging each of the food sources. The widths of the transition arrows indicate the number of times that a robot switched between the corresponding roles. Additionally, we also distinguish between transitioning to the role “*Forage from area 1 or 2*” when there are enough robots already engaging in that role (“*Food full*”) or when there are still foragers needed (“*Food not full*”). The target scenario occurs when robots switch to a foraging role that is not already filled. (d) Evolution of the proportion of robots engaging in each role as over simulation time. The two types of time windows, green and red, represent the absence or presence, respectively, of at least one robot recharging its battery.

in the following equations:

$$E_{\text{agg}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\mathbf{x}_i(T) - \mathbf{c}_i(T)\|_2 \quad (17)$$

$$E_{\text{groups}} = \frac{1}{G} \sum_{k=1}^G \max\left(\frac{G_k(T) - G_k^*}{G_k^*}, 0\right) \quad (18)$$

which separately evaluate aggregation accuracy and the correctness of group sizes. E_{agg} is the average distance between the robots and the center of mass of their group \mathbf{c}_i at the end of the simulation T . Additionally, E_{groups} measures the average number of robots that incorrectly aggregated in a group that already has the target size G_k^* .

Fig. 11(a) summarizes the results of both error metrics for swarm sizes up to 40 robots. In all cases, the robots aggregate into four groups of $N/4$ robots each. For E_{groups} , the number of errors across all swarm sizes tends to cluster near zero, demonstrating the correct performance of the communication module. Although a slight degradation of E_{agg} is visible, the errors remain low even for the largest swarm sizes. This increase in E_{agg} occurs because obstacle avoidance is

prioritized over aggregation, an effect that is more noticeable in larger swarms.

For the second experiment, the formation of geometries, we define the error metric as follows:

$$E_{\text{form}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \min_{j \in \{1, \dots, M\}} \{\|\mathbf{x}_i^*(T) - \mathbf{x}_j(T)\|_2\} \quad (19)$$

which averages the distances between the target points in the formation \mathbf{x}_i^* and the positions of the closest robots \mathbf{x}_j at the final simulation time T . Fig. 11(b) shows a box plot summarizing the error E_{form} for different swarm sizes [target formations shown in Fig. 11(c)]. The results indicate that increasing swarm size causes a slight rise in both the median and dispersion of E_{form} .

Lastly, Fig. 11(c) illustrates scalability in the foraging experiment. In this task, performance is evaluated directly based on the proportion of robots foraging from each food source, with the optimal value being 0.25. The box plot shows that the proportions of foragers from both food areas are very close to the target value of 0.25.

Fig. 11. Scalability results for the three experiments. (a) Box plot showing the error metrics E_{agg} and E_{groups} as the swarm size increases. (b) Box plot showing distribution of the errors E_{form} for increasing swarm sizes. (c) Scalability in the foraging task. It shows the distributions of the proportion of robots foraging from each food source (in green and orange). All the boxes in (a–c) are constructed using samples from 50 independent simulations. (d) Goal formations for each swarm size in (b).

VI. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

The results presented in Section V demonstrated that the proposed communication module can be used to solve three different SR tasks. Moreover, the same evolved communication controller was successfully transferred across all tasks. We obtained promising results in terms of both performance and scalability, representing a step toward standardized, task-agnostic communication systems in SR. In Fig. 7(c), we assessed the distribution of errors and convergence time in a swarm of 30 robots using the proposed communication module. We showed that the system can achieve a median error of around 5 within 700 iterations and converge to a median error of 0 in approximately 2700 time steps. These results outperform the convergence time reported in [27] (see Section I), which is approximately 10 000 time steps.

We verified the scalability of the framework in the three proposed SR tasks. Specifically, we showed that group aggregation, formation control, and foraging tasks can be solved by robot swarms of up to 40, 40, and 60 robots, respectively. In addition to flexibility and scalability, robustness was mainly evaluated in the formation task, where the target topology was changed at runtime using three different formations within the same simulation [see Fig. 9(f)]. We demonstrated that the swarm can react to these changes and adapt to new formation topologies. This experiment represents an initial step toward assessing the robustness of the system in complex missions (e.g., search and rescue) that demand formation changes due to unexpected perturbations (such as changes in terrain or

mission goals). A deeper assessment of the robustness of the system in real robots and across a wider range of unexpected scenarios is an important direction for future work.

A single CTRNN-based communication controller was evolved once and successfully applied across all three tasks. This flexibility was achieved through the *task-agnostic* evolution process and the high degree of decoupling between the communication module and the robot controller. Nonetheless, a task-specific configuration of the robot controller (particularly the set of primitives, the primitive selector, and the priority selector) was required for each experiment. The evolution of a communication controller that produces a virtual navigation which, upon convergence, satisfies (4) offers a suitable solution for SR tasks that require precise division of labor and dynamic role allocation. In the aggregation task, the division of labor arises from the allocation of robots to groups of desired sizes. In the formation task, the roles correspond to positions in the target formation geometry. In other words, robots negotiate via the communication module to determine which positions each should occupy. Finally, in the foraging task—inherently linked to division of labor—the effectiveness of the evolved communication module is further demonstrated: robots dynamically allocate foraging roles (e.g., collecting from different food sources or remaining in the nest) among swarm members. The evolved communication module enables efficient convergence to the required number of robots in each role and supports role switching to compensate for the absence of robots whose batteries were depleted.

The proposed system can be evolved once and then transferred across multiple tasks. However, during development, researchers must manually design the task-dependent low-level primitives. Even though these primitives correspond to very simple robot behaviors (e.g., “go back to the nest”), their design requires human expertise and domain knowledge in SR. This constitutes a limitation, as the efficiency and performance of the evolved communication may be sensitive to suboptimal or poorly designed primitives. Additionally, the purpose of the communication module is not to outperform specialized aggregation, formation, or foraging behaviors in SR. Rather, our aim is to provide flexibility, versatility, and, most importantly, transferability to SR communications. This unavoidably entails sacrificing some task-specific performance in favor of broader task generalization. However, a task-specific fine-tuning of the communication module (e.g., through evolution) could be implemented in each deployment to mitigate potential limitations associated with the use of a task-agnostic communication.

The main limitations of the proposed system are twofold. First, the performance and robustness of the communication module may be limited in constrained and low-range communication scenarios. In such cases, control and communication are restricted locally, and in large swarms or when interrobot distances increase, clustering may emerge. For example, formation control of 30 robots can result in three disconnected clusters, each behaving independently. Once the swarm is split into clusters, it may be difficult to intentionally reaggregate the whole swarm unless some form of long-range communication is available. This limitation is particularly critical in tasks

such as foraging, where robots may need to access the communication states of others located far apart (e.g., one robot in the nest and another in a food area). This issue is not explored in depth in this article and warrants further investigation in future work. Moreover, communication noise and signal interference can further challenge coordination and reduce a swarm's ability to operate effectively. The second limitation involves the reliance on high-level sensors that provide global positional information. This issue could be addressed by employing multiagent localization and social odometry [40], [41] to estimate positions, though at the cost of reduced positional accuracy.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This article proposed a self-organized and distributed communication module that was evolved once and successfully applied across different SR tasks. The core of the proposed module is a communication space in which robots perform collective virtual navigation for task coordination. We demonstrated the flexibility and transferability of the proposed communication module in three SR tasks: 1) aggregation in groups; 2) formation of swarm geometries; and 3) multiplace foraging. We further showed that the module is scalable and was successfully applied to all three tasks.

This study opens several directions for future work. The evolution, discovery, and learning of primitives, primitive selectors, and priorities represent a promising line of research toward eliminating the need for manual design and human intervention. In addition, the communication module should be revisited to address tasks with very constrained and low-range communication. Performance in the SR tasks considered here could also be improved by estimating the relative positions of the robots using techniques, such as multiagent localization or SLAM.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid for providing computing resources on Magerit Supercomputer.

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